

Story Effects on Self-Concept in Memory and Imagination

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Abstract

Some research literature have suggested that stories can influence the self-concept. We want to test whether a narrative does influence people's notions of self in their memory or imagination. Our hypothesis is that being exposed to a story makes one reconstructs one's self in one's memory or imagination to be more aligned with the story's main character. With an experiment, we exposed participants ($n=129$) to two conditions (control: report of facts; treatment: the facts in a story form), and then asked the Likert-scale questions to see whether they report selves in their memory or imagination that resemble the story's main character. Using independent sample t-tests, we found no statistically significant results. Therefore, we failed to reject our Null hypothesis -- there was not enough evidence to reject it.

Keywords: story, narrative, self-concept, mental time travel, memory reconstruction

Introduction

Reading fiction is an immersive process, which involves imagination of and identification with characters. We are intrigued by the literature currently available on the effect of stories and a person's self-concept. A person's self-concept may be found in both their autobiographical memories and imaginations. About memories, we know that studies (Loftus & Palmer, 1974; Rodieger & McDermott, 1995; Schacter, 2012) have shown memories are not like a video-camera's recording of events, but can be changed.

Memories seem distinct from imagination, but Mullally & Maguire (2013) have, in a review paper, compiled evidence that the two may have underlying processes that are linked. If they are linked processes, then an effect of stories on memory might also be an effect on imagination.

Nonetheless, in the stead of memory and imagination, other researchers have focused on the malleability of the self-concept. Djikic & Oatley (2014) and Richter et. al. (2013) both assert that stories can influence one's self-concept. Gabriel & Young (2011) argue that their subjects became part of the narrative the subjects were exposed to.

There is a gap in the literature we found: there is no study that has looked at how stories modify the self-concept in an individual's past memory and future imaginations. In autobiographical memory, we want to know whether the self-concept would be modified merely by an exposure to a story. We aim to measure that by asking the participant Likert-scale questions on autobiographical memory after an exposure to a story, and then rate how closely the self of that recollection resemble the self of the story's main character. For example, if the

character was an anxious person, we want to know if the participant also report an anxious past self.

Moreover, we want to look not just at the past, but also the future self: we want to know whether the individual's self notion would be modified when they imagine a future scenario they find themselves in. We can measure the resemblance of such future self and the story character's self using a similar method used to measure the participant's past self. Our hypothesis is the following: when asked to report past memories or to imagine a future scenario, people that are exposed to a story will report a self that more-closely resembles the story's main character than will those in a control group.

Methods

Participants

Participants are mostly college undergraduate students of a large experimental psychology class, with a small percentage coming from the associates of a few students. The participants that are students are required by the class instructor to participate in this experiment as part of a broader participation in several studies produced by class members. We had 129 participants (after removing rows with NA or missing values), with ages ranging from 18-65 ($M=22$, $SD=6.5$), with 61% female, 39% male, with <1% non-binary or opting "not to say". The study was approved by the IRB.

Materials and Procedures

The materials consist of an online experiment given toward the end of the semester. The Independent Variable was the exposure to the story (control: report of facts; treatment: facts told in a story form). The Dependent Variable was the score of how closely the participant's self-

report -- of autobiographical memory or of an imagined future -- resembled the story's main character.

The participant is directed to a website (Qualtrics). Prior to starting the questionnaire, the participant is asked whether they consent: they proceed only if they consent. After giving consent, the participant will need 30 minutes or less to complete the questionnaire. The participant then is taken through several parts of the questionnaire. The first of these is, they are given a story or a report. (The process to assign a report or a story was random.) After they read the assignment (a story or a report), the participant is given a memory questionnaire. These are Likert questions that ask the participants about past autobiographical events. We score it, with the higher score indicating the participant's past self mirrors very closely the self of the story's character. After completing the memory set of questions, the participant is given imagination questions. These are also Likert questions; they ask the participant to imagine future scenarios. We score it, with higher score indicating the participant's future self resembles the story's character's self very closely. After completing those three sections, the participant is given a test to check whether they can answer questions about the story or the report -- this part is only to ascertain they actually read the first part (story or report) and not just click through the questionnaire. The fifth and last section is the sub-questionnaire on demographics -- we placed this demographics questionnaire last, so it would not pose possible interference or order effect in the participant's journey through the questionnaire.

Results

After all the participants complete the questionnaires, we have their test scores. Using R, we performed an independent sample t-test, and found no statistically significant results

($t(120.76)=-0.39, p=0.70$ for memory assimilation; and $t(121.42)=-0.25, p=0.80$ for the imagination assimilation). Though the results are not significant, attached below are two figures showing the means comparison for both memory assimilation and imagination assimilation: there is no effect.

Figure 1

Memory Assimilation Scores Across the Two Conditions

Note. The error bars in both figures are the standard errors of the mean.

Figure 2

Imagination Assimilation Scores Across the Two Conditions

Discussion

The results do not support our hypothesis, which states that people who are exposed to a story would have a self-concept modified to better resemble the story's main character. With a p -value above 5%, the evidence is not enough to reject the Null hypothesis. Though previous studies in the literature suggest that a person may psychologically embody story characters' personalities, our findings ($n=129$) do not justify claiming the influence is strong enough to change the participant's core notion of their self. Given our p -values, assuming the Null hypothesis is true, the probability is high that we have correctly failed to reject the Null hypothesis. However, with a small effect size, our power is low; hence, if we assume the Null is false, the probability is also quite high that we have failed to reject it in error. So this study does not tell us much.

As such, the design of this study itself is called into question. Maybe we could've used Likert scales with superior validities, instead of relying on face validity as we have done here. Perhaps a better designed study or experiment could better elucidate the question of self-concept malleability under story assimilation. Or perhaps a different -- but related -- avenue with a higher effect size could be found and investigated.

This study's results are not statistically significant, so it has extended our knowledge only by telling us what does not work. Moreover, the study also has not filled the gap in the literature because our β was relatively high, due to the small effect size. So we don't know whether we have made a type 2 error. Future research may better address the theoretical and empirical questions of the link between reading a story and the influence it has on one's self-concept, both the self in one's memory and the self in one's imagination.

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